

Extended Abstract: Understanding Initial Cracking in Bridges via Fiber Bragg Grating Sensor Analysis

The occurrence of "initial cracking" during proof load testing (PLT) in bridges, a brief yet impactful process, holds key insights into the future behavior of these structures. This paper documents the observation of PLT through an FBG sensor (central wavelength of 1554.2nm) in an arch spandrel bridge, pre-constructed and yet to open for public use. By logging data before, during, and after the load testing using a broadband light source and a tunable laser, this study analyzes wavelength shift profiles and their patterns.

The findings illuminate the unique behavior of initial cracking, marked by sudden changes in FBG spectra, albeit with some latency. Even before the PLT session, termed the "acclimatizing window," structural perturbations caused up to a 0.2nm shift in the FBG central wavelength. During PLT, the central wavelength fluctuated between ~1554.1nm to ~1554.3nm, with these fluctuations ceasing post-PLT, as confirmed by tunable laser profiles. This highlights the potential detection of initial crackings not only during but also before the PLT due to inherent loads.

Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBGs) serve as periodic structures in optical fibers, functioning as fiber-based mirrors for specific wavelengths. Under mechanical stress, their central wavelengths alter, offering high sensitivity and immunity to electromagnetic interference, making them valuable for structural health monitoring (SHM).

This study explores a seldom-discussed aspect: the "dry run" PLT using FBG sensors in an arch spandrel bridge before its public use. Previous SHM studies primarily focused on real-time traffic, leaving "dry run" PLT underrepresented. By utilizing spectrometric interrogators and experimental tunable lasers, this research delves into FBG interrogation techniques in this context.

Although previous studies have addressed bridge behavior during PLT using different sensors, attention to FBG sensors during this phase has been limited since 2012. Understanding this brief window becomes critical as subsequent readings post-PLT reflect routine load monitoring, while the structure stabilizes after initial proofing loads.

This paper's key contribution lies in shedding light on the evolution of FBG profiles during the crucial but less-explored PLT period, aiming to bridge gaps in documentation and standardization. Comparative analysis between central wavelength shifts and corresponding signal power, supplemented with source codes, further addresses the highlighted issues.